

Coumarinyl-azo-imidazolium protected and concentration dependent size control of gold nanoparticles (GNPs)

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Abstract : 1,3-Dialkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide ($L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$) is used as a surface modifier to control stability and size of gold nanoparticles (GNPs). The size of GNPs is decreased with increasing concentration of $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ and the molar ratio of GNP : $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ from 4 : 1 to 1 : 2 vary particle size from 22 nm to 2 nm. The imidazolium appended GNPs are characterized by TEM, UV-Vis spectroscopy and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) spectroscopy. These GNPs wrapped by $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ have found to be more stable than tetraoctyl ammonium bromide (TOAB) alone.

Keywords : 1,3-Dialkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide, GNPs, fluorescence, quantum yield, TEM.

Introduction

Metal nanoparticles are challenging field of contemporary research activity and have various unusual properties compared with those of metal atoms or bulk metals^{1,2}. Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) are the most studied nanoparticles those exhibit fascinating surface directed, size dependent properties³⁻⁵. The specific optical properties of the GNPs have attracted much both in the theoretical and experimental field⁶⁻⁸. The surface of GNP is a specific reaction field and has been functionalized mainly employing thiol group^{9,10}. Other surface protectors like imidazolyl derivatives are useful chemical surface modifier. Imidazolium capped stable GNPs have been easily functionalized on the imidazole motif and become a useful communication end^{11,12}. Fluorophore in the vicinity of metal nanostructures may enhance emission intensity. In the vicinity of GNP surface the fluorophore may enhance absorption of light due to the increased electromagnetic field around the nanoparticles and non-radiative coupling from the excited state of the molecule to the localized surface plasmon of the metal nanostructures, which is subsequently radiated by the nanostructures^{13,14}. In this work we use 1,3-dialkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide ($L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$) as

nanoparticle surface capping agent. The concentration of $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ is useful parameter to regulate size of GNPs. Besides, vicinal disposition of coumarinyl, a fluorophore, on GNPs may influence on their optical properties. Coumarin, a phytochemical, has been studied for bio-physical and bio-medical properties¹⁵ and a useful laser dye owing to their high quantum yield of fluorescence and high photostability. The substituent on coumarin affects electronic absorption and emission maxima as well as quantum yields and life time^{16,17}. Herein, we use different spectroscopic probes (UV-Vis, DLS, TEM) to characterize the surface implantation of $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ on GNPs and their photophysical properties.

Experimental Materials

Imidazole, coumarin were of analytical reagent grade purchased from SRL, India. $H[AuCl_4]$, sodium borohydride was Sigma-Aldrich reagent. 1-Bromo-n-alkanes, $n-C_6H_{13}-1-Br$, $n-C_9H_{19}-1-Br$, $n-C_{12}H_{25}-1-Br$, $C_{15}H_{31}-1-Br$ and $C_{18}H_{37}-1-Br$, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as such. All other chemicals and solvents were analytical reagent grade as received. 6-Aminocoumarin was synthesized from coumarin followed by nitration and

subsequent reduction. 2-(Coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazole was synthesized by reported procedure¹⁸.

Physical measurements :

Microanalytical data (C, H, N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra by Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer model Lambda 25; FTIR spectra (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) by Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer model RX-1; the ^1H NMR spectra by Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. Emission was examined by LS 55 Perkin-Elmer spectrofluorimeter at room temperature (298 K) in H_2O and toluene solution under degassed condition. The fluorescence quantum yield of the complexes was determined using anthracene as a reference with known Φ_{R} of 0.27 in methanol. The complex and the reference dye were excited at same wavelength, maintaining nearly equal absorbance (~ 0.1), and the emission spectra were recorded. The area of the emission spectrum was integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield was calculated according to the following equation :

$$\frac{\Phi_{\text{S}}}{\Phi_{\text{R}}} = \left[\frac{A_{\text{S}}}{A_{\text{R}}} \right] \times \left[\frac{(Abs)_{\text{R}}}{(Abs)_{\text{S}}} \right] \times \left[\frac{\eta_{\text{S}}^2}{\eta_{\text{R}}^2} \right]$$

Here, Φ_{S} and Φ_{R} are the fluorescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_{S} and A_{R} are the area under the fluorescence spectra of the sample and the reference, respectively, $(Abs)_{\text{S}}$ and $(Abs)_{\text{R}}$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_{S} and η_{R} are the values of refractive index for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference.

Preparation of the ligands and nano particles :

*Preparation of 1,3-dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide ($\text{L}-(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2^+\text{Br}^-$, **1a**) :*

The synthesis was carried out following the modification of published procedure¹⁹. 2-(Coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazole (0.1 g, 0.416 mmol) was dissolved in dry THF (20 ml) and NaH (50%) (0.03 g) was added in pinch (Scheme 1) and refluxed for 20 min. To this hot solution

Scheme 1. Preparation of 1,3-dialkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide ($\text{L}-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$).

$n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{-1-Br}$ (0.2 g, 1.21 mmol) was added slowly and refluxing continued for another 2 h. Orange red solid mass was deposited on the glass wall. The solution was cooled and filtered; the residue was washed with THF and dried in air. Dry mass was dissolved in water, filtered and slowly evaporated to allow for crystallization. Purity of the product was checked by thin-layer chromatography. Yield, 0.12 g, (60%).

Other compounds were prepared following same procedure in 60–70% yield.

Microanalytical data of the compounds : $\text{L}-(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ (**1a**), m.p. > 300 °C; $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$, Anal. Calcd. C, 58.90; H, 6.75; N, 11.45. Found : C, 58.76; H, 6.70; N, 11.38%; FT-IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1426; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1590. $\text{L}-(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ (**1b**), m.p. > 300 °C; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{45}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$, Anal. Calcd. C, 62.83; H, 7.85; N, 9.77. Found : C, 62.91; H, 7.90; N, 9.65%; FT-IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1432; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1595. $\text{L}-(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ (**1c**), m.p. > 300 °C; $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{57}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$, Anal. Calcd. C, 65.75; H, 8.68; N, 8.52. Found : C, 65.86; H, 8.74; N, 8.58%; FT-IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1426; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1590. $\text{L}-(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ (**1d**), m.p. > 300 °C; $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{69}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$, Anal. Calcd. C, 68.02; H, 9.31; N, 7.56. Found : C, 68.06; H, 9.34; N, 7.50%;

FT-IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1420; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1586. $\text{L}-(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{37})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ (**1e**), m.p. >300 °C; $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{81}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$, Anal. Calcd. C, 69.82; H, 9.82; N, 6.79. Found : C, 69.86; H, 9.77; N, 6.84%; FT-IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1425; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, 1595.

Preparation of gold nanoparticles (GNPs) :

The gold nanoparticles were prepared in a two-phase water/TOAB/toluene system. We modified the synthesis method for azoimidazolium-capped nanoparticles following the basic method developed by Brust²⁰ to avoid direct contact between the coumarinylazo motif and NaBH_4 .

$\text{H}[\text{AuCl}_4]$ (30.0 mM) in aqueous solution (2.5 ml) and a 50 mM TOAB toluene solution (7.5 ml) were mixed together and stirred vigorously for about 20 min. Subsequently, the solution was to separate into two distinct transparent (colourless aqueous and orange-red toluene) phases resulting from a quantitative transfer of Au^{III} ions from the aqueous to the toluene phases. A freshly prepared 0.2 M NaBH_4 aqueous solution (4 ml) was slowly added to the two phase reaction mixture with vigorous stirring that was continued for two hours to complete the reaction. The wine red organic phase was separated and then mixed with 1,3-dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-imidazolium bromide aqueous solution (2 ml) while stirring. After sometime, the red aqueous solution of 1,3-dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide becomes colourless due to the transfer of ligand from aqueous to toluene medium and wine red toluene medium becomes reddish colour. Depending on concentration of 1,3-dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide four sets are prepared.

Set-1; GNP : 1,3-Dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-imidazolium bromide in 4 : 1 molar ratio.

Set-2; GNP : 1,3-Dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-imidazolium bromide in 2 : 1 molar ratio.

Set-3; GNP : 1,3-Dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-imidazolium bromide in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

Set-4; GNP : 1,3-Dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-imidazolium bromide in 1 : 2 molar ratio.

Similar solution sets were prepared using other salts.

Results and discussion

1,3-Dialkyl-2-(coumarinylazo)imidazolium bromides ($\text{L}-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$; n = 6 (**1a**, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}^-$), 9 (**1b**, $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}^-$), 12 (**1c**, $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}^-$), 15 (**1d**, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}^-$), 18 (**1e**, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{38}^-$) are synthesised from alkylation of 2-(coumarinylazo)imidazole (Scheme 1)^{18,19}. The molecules are conducting in aqueous medium and molar conductances are 119 (**1a**), 115 (**1b**), 92 (**1c**), 100 (**1d**) and 109 (**1e**) $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and support 1 : 1 electrolytic feature of the molecules. Melting points and other general features are given in experimental section. The molecules are structurally established by spectroscopic (FT-IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR) data. Mass spectral data support molecular ion peaks at calculated position.

Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) :

Following Brust²⁰ procedure GNPs are prepared by the reduction of HAuCl_4 with NaBH_4 in presence of TOAB stabilizer. They have a relatively narrow distribution in size and their number-average size was 12.5 nm with the standard deviation of 1.90 nm. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) is used to determine distribution pattern of different categories of GNPs produced in solution. The hydrodynamic diameter (dh) and the polydispersity index (PDI) of the nanoparticles dispersed in water/toluene microemulsion media are estimated at different ω values. The PDI values are all close to 0.1 indicating that the nanodroplets are fairly monodisperse. Fig. 1 shows the particle size distribution of GNPs at different ω using dynamic light scattering technique. Average diameter of the particles obtained from this technique are 4.0 nm at $\omega = 5$, 5.0 nm at $\omega = 10$, 14 nm at $\omega = 15$ and 20 nm at $\omega = 20$, in accordance with the results shown by TEM are 4.0 nm ($\omega = 5$), 5.0 nm ($\omega = 10$), 12 nm ($\omega = 15$) and 15 nm ($\omega = 20$). The reported particle sizes are within $\pm 5\%$.

Spectral studies :

The IR spectra of azo compounds exhibit peaks at 1721–1737 cm^{-1} and can be assigning as ν_{COO} stretching on comparing with 6-nitrocoumarine (ν_{COO} , at 1742 cm^{-1}) and 6-aminocoumarin (ν_{COO} , 1705 cm^{-1}). 1,3-Dialkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-imidazolium bromide (L -

Fig.1. GNP particle size distribution at $\omega = 5, 10, 15$ and 20 using dynamic light scattering technique.

(C_nH_{2n+1}) $_2^+Br^-$) show $\nu_{N=N}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ at $1418-1442$ and $1535-1555\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively and ν_{COO} appears at $1710-1735\text{ cm}^{-1}$. GNPs embedded $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ exhibit shifting of $\nu_{N=N}$ ($1400-1410\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_{C=N}$ ($1510-1525\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to lower frequency compared to free ligand data which may imply charge transfer from electron rich GNP surface to π -acidic azoimidazolium pro-tector.

The 1H NMR spectra of the azo compounds are recorded in CD_3CN and the assignment has been done on the basis of spin-spin interaction and substituent effect

(Table 1). The proton numbering is depicted in Scheme 1. The 12-H and 7-H proton lies in downfield region at >8.00 ppm. The 8-H and 9-H protons come at $6.45-6.60$ ppm and $6.51-6.62$ ppm region respectively. 1-3-Dialkyl protons show very complex splitting and difficult to assign. The coumarinyl protons appear at down field side at $6.6-7.7$ ppm.

Absorption and emission spectroscopy :

The absorption and emission spectra of the compounds are taken in methanol solution. The compounds exhibit three bands at $250-600$ nm with high molar extinction

Table 1. ^1H NMR spectroscopic data of $\text{CAI}-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$

Compd.	4-H ^a	5-H ^a	7-H ^d	8-H ^b	9-H ^b	11-H ^c	12-H ^b	12-CH ₂ ^a	-(CH ₂) _{n-1} -CH ₃ [*]
1a	7.17	7.17	7.60	5.78 (9.0)	6.46 (9.0)	6.71	7.62 (9.0)	3.37	1.54–1.25
1b	7.15	7.15	7.60	5.77 (9.0)	6.46 (9.0)	6.70	7.60 (9.0)	3.40	1.58–1.30
1c	7.15	7.15	7.62	5.75 (9.0)	6.43 (9.0)	6.68	7.62 (9.0)	3.40	1.55–1.20
1d	7.17	7.17	7.60	5.76 (9.0)	6.44 (9.0)	6.60	7.65 (9.0)	3.30	1.56–1.25
1e	7.15	7.15	7.62	5.70 (9.0)	6.40 (9.0)	6.60	7.67 (9.0)	3.40	1.59–1.25
GNP@1a	7.05	7.05	6.55	5.65 (7.00)	6.25 (7.00)	6.55	7.60 (7.00)	3.30	1.50–1.20
GNP@1b	7.03	7.03	6.55	5.68 (7.00)	6.30 (7.00)	6.65	7.60 (7.00)	3.35	1.50–1.24
GNP@1c	7.05	7.05	6.50	5.65 (7.00)	6.28 (7.00)	6.60	7.63 (7.00)	3.30	1.50–1.25
GNP@1d	7.05	7.05	6.55	5.65 (7.00)	6.35 (7.00)	6.60	7.63 (7.00)	3.30	1.50–1.20
GNP@1e	7.05	7.05	6.57	5.68 (7.00)	6.26 (7.00)	6.58	7.64 (7.00)	3.30	1.50–1.20

^aBroad; ^bdoublet; ^cmultiplet; ^dsinglet.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2^+$, (GNP encapsulated) (a) for pure GNPs, (b) for 4 : 1 (Set-1), (c) for 2 : 1 (Set-2), (d) for 1 : 1 (Set-3), (e) for 1 : 2 (Set-4).

coefficient value (ϵ , $103\text{--}104\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The band at $360\text{--}380\text{ nm}$ on alkylation shifts to longer wavelength, $375\text{--}401\text{ nm}$ (Fig. 2, Table 2)²¹. Sharp SPM (Surface Plasmon Band) of GNP appears at 533 nm in aqueous

medium. $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+$ spectra in toluene show blue shift of Plasmon band by $16\text{--}44\text{ nm}$ (Table 2); with increasing amount of $L-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ to GNP the SPM has shifted to shorter wavelength (blue shift), e.g., $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2^+$ at 4 : 1 molar ratio, 522 nm ; 2 : 1 molar ratio, 510 nm ; 1 : 1 molar ratio, 502 nm and 1 : 2 molar ratio, 489 nm . Increase in chain length of $-\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}$ has little influence and show blue shift in general, e.g., at 4 : 1 molar ratio $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2^+$, 522 nm ; $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19})_2^+$, 520 nm ; $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25})_2^+$, 518 nm ; $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31})_2^+$, 517 nm ; $\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{37})_2^+$, 514 nm .

Fluorescence spectra of $L-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ are recorded in methanol and show emission at $447\text{--}495\text{ nm}$ upon excitation at $375\text{--}380\text{ nm}$. The fluorescence quantum yields of $L-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ are very low, 0.0002 to 0.0003 while it is increased by 3–25 times upon impregnation on GNPs. The presence of nearby metallic films or nanoparticles ($\text{GNP}@L-(\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+$) has affected the emission characteristics of fluorophores in terms of in-

Table 2. Absorption and emission spectroscopic data of L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺Br⁻ in water and GNP encapsulated ligand (GNP@L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺Br⁻) in different concentration ratio in toluene

GNP : L-(C ₆ H ₁₃) ₂ ⁺ Br ⁻ (molar ratio) [†]	UV-Vis data λ _{max} (nm)		Fluorescence data		Quantum yield			
	π-π*	Surface plasmon band	λ _{ex} (nm)	λ _{em} (nm)	(Φ)	10 ⁻⁵ k _r	10 ⁻⁸ k _{nr}	τ (ns)
L-(C ₆ H ₁₃) ₂ ⁺ Br ⁻ (1a)	380		380	447, 495	0.0002	2.30	11.50	0.871
4 : 1	390	522	390	450, 610	0.00062	2.35	4.64	2.15
2 : 1	398	510	398	460, 610	0.00069	3.12	3.81	2.62
1 : 1	389	502	389	460, 611	0.0018	3.42	3.75	2.66
1 : 2	394	489	394	477, 614	0.0050	3.69	2.99	3.35
L-(C ₉ H ₁₉) ₂ ⁺ Br ⁻ (1b)	380		380	447, 495	0.00025	2.72	10.90	0.919
4 : 1	392	520	392	456, 615	0.0012	2.96	6.35	1.15
2 : 1	389	509	389	447, 526	0.0028	3.50	5.34	1.57
1 : 1	395	499	395	456, 562	0.0035	3.51	4.50	3.35
1 : 2	397	495	397	482, 624	0.0055	3.79	3.21	4.5
L-(C ₁₂ H ₂₅) ₂ ⁺ Br ⁻ (1c)	378		378	462	0.00025	2.72	10.90	0.919
4 : 1	392	518	392	456, 615	0.0012	3.79	8.12	1.05
2 : 1	396	508	396	456, 562	0.0052	3.50	5.34	1.23
1 : 1	396	506	396	463, 548	0.0052	4.22	4.50	1.43
L-(C ₁₅ H ₃₁) ₂ ⁺ Br ⁻ (1d)	380		380	456	0.0003	4.16	13.90	0.720
4 : 1	392	517	392	456, 615	0.0012	3.79	5.34	2.15
2 : 1	395	508	395	463, 548	0.0028	3.50	4.50	2.66
1 : 1	390	504	390	437, 530	0.0031	4.85	4.41	2.67
L-(C ₁₈ H ₃₇) ₂ ⁺ Br ⁻ (1e)	375		375	463	0.00027	4.54	16.80	0.594
4 : 1	392	514	392	456, 615	0.0012	2.79	5.34	0.895
2 : 1	401	509	401	463, 615	0.0016	2.80	4.59	1.68
1 : 1	388	507	388	455, 531	0.0064	3.39	5.30	1.89

[†]Concentration ratio GNP@L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺Br⁻ (**1**) in toluene at high concentration of CAI-C_n⁺Br⁻ did not extracted ligand completely to toluene medium. Alkyl group, -C₁₂H₂₅, -C₁₅H₃₁, -C₁₈H₃₇ showed strict limit of extraction as 1 : 1 (GNP : L-(C₆H₁₃)₂⁺Br⁻).

creasing the quantum yields of fluorescent molecules and subsequently improved photostabilities^{13,14}. Surface embedded fluorophore on the nanostructure may enhance the electromagnetic field produced by plasmonic nanostructures (Fig. 3) and may couple with light to fluorescent dye molecules in the immediate environment, thereby providing the extreme signal amplification.

Lifetime data of the compounds of L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺Br⁻ are taken in methanol solvent on excitation at 370 nm. The decay profiles fit with biexponential curve (Fig. 4) and the average lifetime of free ligands lie in between 0.594 to 0.919 ns and GNP@L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺ show longer life time, 0.895–3.35 ns (Table 2). In general, metallic nanoparticles have been shown to decrease the excited-state lifetimes of vicinal fluorophores^{14,21}. However, the

enhancement of life-time in the case of GNP@L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺ may be attributed to the reduction of PET (Coumarin (π*)→ Imidazolium (π*)) and vibrational relaxation due to imidazolium coating on the GNP surface (Scheme 3).

TEM analyses :

A TEM grid coated with a thin polymeric support film has been deposited with samples by evaporating a drop of solution under vacuum. Images are captured and have been analysed by inbuilt software. Image analysis shows more or less spherical particle and size of GNPs lie within 2–22 nm and average particle size is 18 nm for TOAB coated nano particles in toluene. Gold nano preparation followed by extraction to toluene medium by adding L-(C_nH_{2n+1})₂⁺Br⁻ at different proportion has been

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of (a) Set-1, (b) Set-2, (c) Set-3, (d) Set-4.

Scheme 3. Cartoon shows formation of micelle (TOAB) stabilized GNPs, substitution of stabiliser by fluorophore with imidazolium capping group over GNPs and light irradiation shows emission from pendant coumarinyl motif.

used to deposit on grid and TEM images (Fig. 5). Thus long alkyl substituted imidazolium motif encapsulates GNPs and reduces their size. With increasing concentration of ligand $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$ GNPs size decreases (Fig 5). This favors synthesis of targeted nano size as per one's desire by controlling concentration of ligand and its alkyl chain length.

Conclusion

1,3-Dialkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide ($L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$) is used as nanoparticles stabilizer and size regulator. These are characterized by NMR, IR and conductance measurement. The imidazolium stabilised GNPs are characterized using TEM, UV-Vis spectroscopy and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) spectroscopy. These synthesized GNPs wrapped with $L-(C_nH_{2n+1})_2^+Br^-$

Fig. 4. Decay profile of (a) Set-1, (b) Set-2, (c) Set-3, (d) Set-4 and (e) Set-5 1,3-dihexyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazolium bromide.

Fig. 5. TEM images of GNPs in different concentration ratio of (i) $\text{GNP@L-(C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2^+$ and (ii) $\text{GNP@L-(C}_{12}\text{H}_{25})_2^+$.

are found to be more stable than tetra-octyl ammonium bromide (TOAB) alone. The fluorescence, quantum yield and life time of $\text{GNP@L-(C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1})_2^+\text{Br}^-$ are higher than free ligands.

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References

1. M. A. Hayat, "Colloidal gold : Principles, methods, and applications", Academic Press, San Diego, 1989.
2. P. P. P. Edwards and J. Meurig, *Angew. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 5480.
3. C. P. Collier, T. Vossmeier and J. R. Heath, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1998, **49**, 371.
4. M. P. Pileni, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2001, **105**, 3358.
5. Y. Yang and P. Burkhard, *J. Nanobio.*, 2012, **10**, 42.
6. G. Yin, S.-Y. Wang, M. Xu and L.-Y. Chen, *J. Korean Phys. Soc.*, 2006, **49**, 2108.
7. M. Quinten, "Optical Properties of Nanoparticle Systems : Mie and Beyond", Wiley-VCH, 2011.
8. T. K. Sau, A. Pal, N. R. Jana, Z. L. Wang and T. Pal, *J. Nano. Res.*, 2001, **3**, 257.
9. P. D. Jadzinsky, G. Calero, C. J. Ackerson, D. A. Bushnell and R. D. Kornberg, *Science*, 2007, **318**, 430.
10. K.-H. Lee, Y.-S. Lin and P. J. Huang, *J. Nanomaterials*, 2013, **1**.
11. M.-A. Neouze *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2010, **20**, 9593.
12. U. K. Sarkar, D. K. Debnath and W. Hossain, *J. Mol. Str.*, 2014, **1061**, 104.
13. A. Leitner, M. E. Lippitsch, S. Draxler, M. Reigler and F. R. Aussenegg, *Appl. Phys. B : Lasers Opt.*, 1985, **36**, 105.
14. A. Sanchez-Gonzalez, S. Corni and B. Mennucci *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2011, **115**, 5450.
15. S. Mirunalini and M. Krishnaveni, *International J. Pharm. Tech. Res.*, 2011, **3**, 1693.
16. S. Roy, T. K. Mondal, P. Mitra, E. Lopez-Torres and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 913.
17. S. Roy, T. K. Mondal, P. Mitra and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2013, **51**, 27.
18. P. Datta, D. Sardar, P. Mitra and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 1516.
19. A. Nandi, C. Sen, D. Mallick, R. K. Sinha and C. Sinha, *Adv. Mater. Phys. Chem.*, 2013, **3**, 133.
20. M. Brust, M. Walker, D. Bethell, D. J. Schiffrin and R. Whyman, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 801.
21. P. Gayen, T. K. Misra and C. Sinha, *J. Spectrosc. Dyn.*, 2014, **4**, 27.

